

SQUEEZE CASTING AND CHARACTERIZATION OF AL₂O_{3p}/ZL102 COMPOSITE

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SUMMARY: In this research, the Al₂O_{3p} / ZL102 composite is used for the squeeze casting and metal module casting respectively. Its microstructure is characterized by optical microscope and scanning electron microscope (SEM). Its tensile strength, elongation and wear resistance are tested. The optimum pressure parameters of squeeze casting are achieved based on the above characterization. The results show that by use of the technique of squeeze casting, the microstructure become dense and the pore defects which usually appeared in metal module casting are completely eliminated, the binding force between the Al₂O₃ particles and metal matrixes is increased. The surface of the specimen become smooth and bright. The tensile strength, elongation and wear resistance are improved compared with that of metal module casting.

KEYWORDS: squeeze casting, metal module casting, Al₂O₃ particles, ZL102, tensile strength, elongation, wear resistance

INTRODUCTION

During the past 30 years, the metal matrix composites (MMCs) have been paid more attention for its advanced properties. This kind of material is developed rapidly in the advanced techniques area, esp. in the area of military, aeronautics and astronautics [1, 2]. Up to date, a series techniques are used to prepare MMCs, which can be divided into three types according to the state of metal matrix during synthesis: (1) liquid synthesis, (2) solid synthesis, (3) two-phase-area synthesis. However, the application of MMCs is still limited because of some problems, e.g. the interface reaction, high oxygen content, gas content and cinder content, complicated technology and high cost etc. [3, 4].

Recently, the squeeze casting techniques are used in the production of fiber reinforced metal matrix, and shows some obvious advantages than the common technology [5]. In this paper, we report our research on the production of Al₂O_{3p} / ZL102 composite by the squeezes casting technique.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The average diameter of Al_2O_3 particles used in this experiment is in the range of $0.3\mu\text{m}\sim 1\mu\text{m}$. The ZL102 alloy is chosen as the metal matrix. The chemical composition of ZL102 alloy is shown in table 1.

Table 1: Chemical composition of ZL102(wt%)

Si	Cu	Fe	Al
12.5	0.01	0.05	87.4

The $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{ZL102}$ composite is prepared by adding the pre-heated 6% Al_2O_3 particles at the temperature of 200°C into the ZL102 alloy at the state of semi-solidification by a method of mechanical stirring. Afterwards, the semi-solidified alloy is heated to the temperature of $710\sim 730^\circ\text{C}$ for squeeze casting. The squeeze casting module is schematically drawn in figure 1. It was pre-heated to $250\sim 300^\circ\text{C}$ before pouring.

*Fig.1: Schematically drawn of squeeze casting module
1-roof of upper module, 2-upper module, 3-squeeze head,
4-lower module, 5-casting, 6-push pole, 7- roof of lower module*

The technological parameters of squeeze casting are shown in table 2.

Table 2: Squeeze casting parameters

pouring temperature ($^\circ\text{C}$)	module temperature ($^\circ\text{C}$)	pressure (MPa)	holding time (s)
710~730	250~300	0~115	60

The microstructures of Al_2O_3 / ZL102 Composites are analyzed by optical microscope and scanning electron microscope (SEM). According to the ASTM standard, the tensile specimen is prepared for the testing of tensile strength and elongation. The wear resistance of Al_2O_3 / ZL102 composite is tested.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Under the observation of optical microscope, the Al_2O_3 particles distribute uniformly in the matrix of ZL102 (see Fig.2).

Fig.2: Distribution of Al_2O_3 particles in the matrix of ZL102 (pressure: 85MPa).

Fig.2 also shows that most of the Al_2O_3 particles usually distribute in the grain boundary, which is related to the solidification process. It can be sure that the Al_2O_3 particles uniformly distributed in the grain boundary will be able to effectively resist the deformation of matrix and reinforce the ZL102 alloy. By use of SEM, the microstructure of the Al_2O_3 / ZL102 composite is observed at high magnification. The results indicated that pore defects which often appeared in the metal module castings are completely eliminated and the microstructure become dense. Compared with that of metal castings, the surface brightness is improved. This is attributed to the reason that the filling ability of liquid Al_2O_3 / ZL102 composite is improved by the squeezing force.

The tensile strength and elongation of squeeze castings versus the pressure are shown in figure 3. It reveals that tensile strength and elongation of squeeze castings are higher than that of metal module castings (pressure=0) and are increased with the increase of pressure. However, when the pressure is over 85MPa, the tensile strength is increased slowly with the increase of pressure. Whereas the elongation get its optimum values at the pressure of 85MPa. This is due to the reason that with the increase of pressure, the pores in the matrix is eliminated and the binding force between the matrix and the particle is increased, which made the tensile strength and elongation increased. But if the pressure is too high, the resistance of Al_2O_3 particles to the deformation of matrix is greatly increased and the elongation is decreased. Therefore, the brittleness is increased.

Fig.3: The tensile strength and elongation of Al₂O_{3p}/ZL102 Composite versus the pressure.

Fig.4 represents the wear resistance of Al₂O_{3p}/ZL102 composite versus the pressure.

Fig.4: Wear resistance of Al₂O_{3p}/ZL102 composite versus the pressure.

The wear resistance of $Al_2O_{3p} / ZL102$ is mainly determined by its tensile strength. Fig.4 indicated that the wear resistance also increases with the increase of pressure, but it is increased slowly as the pressure is over 85MPa. Based on the results of Fig.3 and Fig.4, the optimum pressure value in this experiment is determined as 85MPa.

CONCLUSIONS

1. By use of the technique of squeeze casting, the pore defects in MMCs can be completely eliminated, the tensile strength, elongation and wear resistance can be greatly improved.
2. The optimum pressure can be determined according to the variation of mechanical properties versus pressure. In this research, the optimum pressure is determined as 85MPa.
3. The improvement of squeeze casting to the quality of $Al_2O_{3p} / ZL102$ composite is attributed to the fact that the binding force between the Al_2O_3 particles and ZL102 matrix is increased and the pore defects is eliminated under the squeeze force.

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